

Monetary Policy in Developing Economies: The Case of Puerto Rico

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Research Article

Abstract

This paper analyzes the role and limits of monetary policy in developing economies under conditions of constrained or absent monetary sovereignty, using Puerto Rico as a critical case study. Conventional macroeconomic theory treats monetary policy as a central stabilization tool, yet this presumes institutional capacities such as currency issuance, interest rate control, and lender-of-last-resort functions that many developing or non-sovereign economies lack. As a fully dollarized and non-sovereign U.S. territory, Puerto Rico represents an extreme case in which monetary policy is entirely externalized to the U.S. Federal Reserve, whose decisions reflect mainland economic conditions rather than local needs. The paper contrasts mainstream monetary frameworks, particularly Monetarist and New Keynesian approaches, with heterodox perspectives drawn from Post-Keynesian, Structuralist, Dependency, and Modern Monetary Theory traditions. It argues that orthodox models overstate the benefits of credibility and price stability while understating the economic costs of externally imposed monetary regimes in contexts marked by weak transmission mechanisms, structural unemployment, and fiscal constraint. Using existing empirical evidence, the analysis highlights the asymmetric labor market effects of U.S. monetary policy in Puerto Rico and the limited explanatory power of inflation-focused frameworks. The paper concludes that while Puerto Rico's stagnation cannot be resolved within its current monetary arrangement, limited policy space exists through institutional innovation, particularly via the strengthening of local financial institutions and development-oriented credit mechanisms, and that non-sovereign economies expose fundamental limits in conventional monetary policy paradigms.

JEL Classification: E52, O11, B52

Keywords: Monetary sovereignty, Dollarization, Development macroeconomics, Puerto Rico

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1. Introduction

What role can monetary policy play in a developing economy that lacks sovereignty over its currency, interest rates, and financial institutions? In standard economic models, monetary policy is a powerful tool used to smooth business cycles, control inflation, stimulate growth, and ensure long-term macroeconomic stability. But in practice, especially for developing economies, its effectiveness is often shaped less by theory and more by political and structural realities. In many cases, monetary authorities must navigate severe institutional constraints, narrow policy spaces, and external influences. For countries and territories that are heavily dependent on foreign capital, operate under dollarized regimes, or lack a central bank entirely, the standard toolkit of monetary policy becomes far more limited, sometimes even irrelevant (Mishra & Montiel, 2013; Calvo & Reinhart, 2002; Sharpe, 2014).

Puerto Rico represents one of the clearest examples of these limitations, as evidenced by its prolonged economic stagnation, an unemployment rate that averaged over 10% from 2006 to 2019, and a population decline of more than 14% between 2010 and 2020, largely due to emigration driven by economic hardship (Krueger, 2015). As an unincorporated territory of the United States, Puerto Rico does not issue its own currency, cannot set its own interest rates, and has no control over money supply or liquidity. The island is fully dollarized and completely dependent on the decisions made by the U.S. Federal Reserve, an institution whose policies are determined based on the macroeconomic conditions of the continental United States, not the Caribbean. Unlike U.S. states, Puerto Rico lacks formal representation in the Federal Reserve's monetary policymaking process, meaning that it is subjected to external macroeconomic decisions without any political or institutional leverage to influence them (Krueger, 2015). This dependence is reflected empirically in the strong unemployment response to U.S. interest rate hikes (Aleamar & Rodríguez, 2025).

This structural arrangement has deep implications for how economic crises are managed, and often mismanaged, on the island. Without a central bank, Puerto Rico cannot use conventional monetary tools to address recessions, reduce unemployment, or control inflation. During periods of economic downturn, such as the prolonged recession beginning in 2006 or the fiscal crisis that culminated in the imposition of the PROMESA oversight board in 2016, policymakers in Puerto Rico were left with only limited fiscal levers and constrained access to credit. The absence of monetary autonomy in such a context has contributed to what many scholars describe as a chronic condition of dependency and underdevelopment (Catalá Oliveras, 2016).

In this sense, Puerto Rico stands as a case study in what happens when monetary policy becomes externalized. Yet it also serves as a critical site for testing the limits of conventional economic theory, even as proponents of mainstream frameworks might argue that rule-based regimes, despite their rigidity, offer credibility and discipline to small, open economies, particularly in contexts with a history of inflation or weak institutional trust, while exploring the insights offered by heterodox perspectives. Mainstream economists often argue that developing economies can benefit from rule-based monetary regimes, inflation targeting, and central bank independence. These policies, rooted in the work of economists such as Friedman (1968) and Taylor (1993), assume that stable macroeconomic environments lead to long-term investment and sustainable growth. Institutions such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank have championed these ideas, pushing for inflation targeting regimes and fiscal orthodoxy in the Global South.

However, as critics have pointed out, such approaches often fail to account for the structural features that define many developing economies: external debt, commodity dependence, volatile capital flows, weak institutional capacity, and limited monetary sovereignty. For economies like Puerto Rico, which lack

even the minimal tools of sovereign monetary policy, the orthodox frameworks become not only difficult to implement but actively counterproductive. They assume a degree of autonomy that simply does not exist (Dos Santos, 1970). Furthermore, even where formal sovereignty exists, for many developing countries the binding constraint isn't the fiscal deficit itself but the balance of payments through persistent account deficits, currency hierarchies, and the need to hold foreign reserves sharply limit the policy share available even to nominally sovereign currency issuers (Vernengo & Pérez, 2020).

This has led to the rise of alternative frameworks that seek to rethink the relationship between money, the state, and economic development. Post-Keynesian and Structuralist economists argue that money is endogenous, created through the banking system in response to demand, and that central banks should play a developmental role by financing public investment and facilitating structural transformation (Lavoie, 2014; Epstein, 2006). Dependency theorists go further, arguing that monetary subordination is a symptom of deeper forms of colonial and neocolonial economic control (Dos Santos, 1970; Catalá Oliveras, 2016). More recently, Modern Monetary Theory (MMT) has gained attention for its redefinition of the role of fiscal policy in sovereign economies, emphasizing that currency-issuing governments can sustain higher levels of deficit spending, though critics of MMT caution that this can lead to inflationary pressures or undermine investor confidence if real resource constraints are ignored or if fiscal credibility is questioned without the risks commonly asserted in orthodox models (Kelton, 2020; Vernengo & Pérez, 2020).

Each of these perspectives offers a different lens for understanding Puerto Rico's monetary predicament. The post-Keynesian view reveals the limitations of relying on credit creation in an economy without a central lender of last resort. Structuralist arguments highlight the disjuncture between Puerto Rico's economic needs and the monetary regime it is trapped within. Dependency theory frames the issue as part of a larger political and economic system of domination, where the absence of monetary sovereignty reflects the broader absence of self-determination. And while MMT cannot fully apply to Puerto Rico, since the island does not issue its own currency, it still invokes important questions about the artificial constraints imposed by fiscal austerity and external control (Kelton, 2020; Sharpe, 2014).

The aim of this paper is to analyze the nature and limitations of monetary policy in both developing and non-sovereign economies, a distinction that is especially relevant for the case of Puerto Rico. While developing economies typically retain formal monetary sovereignty but operate under structural constraints, non-sovereign entities like Puerto Rico function within externalized monetary frameworks imposed by larger political structures, leaving them with even fewer policy tools and no formal control over monetary institutions. In developing economies, using Puerto Rico as a critical case study. It will do so by engaging with both mainstream and heterodox schools of thought, examining how each conceptualizes the role of monetary policy in contexts of underdevelopment, and how Puerto Rico aligns (or does not align) with those frameworks.

The first section of the paper explores the foundations of mainstream monetary policy. It begins with a discussion of Monetarist and New Keynesian models, tracing their assumptions about inflation control, price stability, and interest rate management. It then examines the difficulties of applying these models to developing economies, focusing on issues such as financial market depth, inflation volatility, and exchange rate rigidity. Special attention is given to dollarization, a common phenomenon in developing economies and the central monetary characteristic of Puerto Rico. This section concludes with an analysis of how the absence of a central bank and the island's reliance on U.S. monetary policy shapes its macroeconomic outcomes.

The second section introduces heterodox critiques, beginning with Post-Keynesian and Structuralist perspectives. These traditions argue for a developmentalist orientation to monetary policy, one that

prioritizes employment, investment, and redistribution. It then turns to dependency theory, situating Puerto Rico within a broader historical pattern of external economic domination and fiscal austerity. The section also considers the applicability of Modern Monetary Theory in non-sovereign settings and discusses policy innovations that might be possible within the current political and monetary limitations, such as local credit creation or cooperative finance.

The third and final section offers a set of conclusions and policy recommendations. It argues that Puerto Rico's current economic stagnation cannot be resolved within the constraints of the current monetary arrangement. However, meaningful change may still be possible through institutional reforms, credit creation strategies, and the strengthening of local financial institutions. The paper closes by suggesting future research avenues, particularly in examining the asymmetric effects of U.S. monetary policy on the Puerto Rican economy and the potential for fiscal-monetary coordination even in non-sovereign contexts.

Understanding Puerto Rico's monetary condition is not simply an academic exercise. It reflects broader questions about sovereignty, development, and the boundaries of economic theory. In a time where many developing economies remain vulnerable to external shocks, unresponsive monetary regimes, and fiscal orthodoxy, Puerto Rico's experience offers both a cautionary tale and an urgent call to rethink the fundamentals of economic governance.

2. Mainstream Perspectives on Monetary Policy in Developing Economies

Mainstream Economics presents monetary policy as a neutral and technical tool through which central banks maintain macroeconomic stability by either adjusting interest rates or by influencing money supply. This view goes off the assumption of monetary sovereignty: that governments possess independent central banks capable of setting policy in alignment with national economic goals. However, in practice, especially in developing economies, these assumptions often start breaking down due to institutional weaknesses, external dependencies, and limited policy autonomy (Taylor, 1993; Friedman, 1968). The union of Monetarist and New Keynesian frameworks forms the backbone of orthodox monetary thinking. Milton Friedman (1968) famously argued that inflation is "always and everywhere a monetary phenomenon," emphasizing the control of money supply as the most important task for monetary authorities. He advocated for predictable, rules-based approaches to monetary policy, warning that discretionary interventions often produce instability. Friedman's ideas would lay the foundations for central bank independence and a de-emphasis away from fiscal activism.

Building on these Monetarist insights, New Keynesian economists introduced nominal rigidities and forward-looking expectations into monetary models. John Taylor (1993) proposed the Taylor Rule, a formula prescribing interest rate adjustments based on deviations of inflation and output from their targets. This approach to policy, based on rules, aimed to increase the credibility and transparency of central banks. In these models, inflation targeting would come out as the dominant policy framework, positioning central banks as the guardians of price stability and tying inflation expectations to the credibility of institutions.

Later on, by the early 2000s, inflation targeting and central bank independence would become standard prescriptions in the policy toolkits of the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank. Many developing countries then adopted these frameworks through structural adjustment programs or institutional reforms. The underlying rationale was that credible monetary policy would lower inflation expectations, attract foreign investment, and encourage long-term growth (Taylor, 1993).

However, empirical evidence suggests that these outcomes have been uneven. Mishra and Montiel (2013), in a review of monetary transmission in developing countries, argue that financial markets in these contexts are often shallow, informal, and segmented. This fragmentation weakens the transmission mechanism between central bank policy rates and market outcomes. For example, bank lending may be constrained by high-risk premiums or capital flight, while inflation expectations remain unanchored due to institutional mistrust. Developing economies' vulnerability to external shocks further complicate monetary management. Commodity price volatility, sudden capital flow reversals, and geopolitical risks make it difficult to implement consistent, forward-looking, and long-term policy. Central banks may face political pressure to accommodate fiscal deficits, risking inflation or reputational damage. These constraints limit the effectiveness of rule-based monetary regimes and call into question the universal applicability of inflation targeting.

A particularly difficult challenge for many developing economies is the phenomenon of dollarization, the widespread use of foreign currency, either formally or informally. In some countries, such as Ecuador and El Salvador, the U.S. dollar is adopted as legal tender. In others, dollarization occurs de facto, especially in the banking system. Calvo and Reinhart (2002) coined the term "fear of floating" to describe how ostensibly flexible exchange rate regimes often behave like fixed systems because of the risks associated with currency depreciation, such as inflation, debt distress, or capital flight. In dollarized economies, the scope for independent monetary policy is extremely limited. These countries cannot conduct open market operations in their own currency, serve as lenders of last resort, or set interest rates according to domestic needs. As a result, monetary conditions are effectively imported from the anchor country, typically the United States, which sets policy based on its own macroeconomic conditions. The result is a form of macroeconomic pass-through in which local business cycles are heavily influenced by foreign interest rate decisions (Calvo & Reinhart, 2002). Alemar and Rodríguez (2025) further demonstrate this point empirically in Puerto Rico's case, finding that increases in U.S. interest rates are associated with significant rises in unemployment, even though they do not explain much of the variation in Puerto Rican inflation numbers.

While dollarization can reduce currency risk and inflation volatility, it comes at a steep cost in terms of lost flexibility. External shocks, such as a rise in U.S. interest rates, can trigger recessions in dollarized economies by increasing the cost of borrowing and inducing capital outflows. Without a central bank to respond with counter-cyclical measures, these economies often resort to procyclical fiscal adjustments, raising taxes or cutting spending, which exacerbates downturns. For instance, countries like Panama, which have long operated under dollarized regimes, face limits on liquidity management and crisis response. While they benefit from currency stability and integration into global financial systems, they are vulnerable to liquidity crunches and financial contagion during global downturns. Without local currency instruments, their policy options during crises are significantly narrower than those available to sovereign issuers with monetary autonomy (Mishra & Montiel, 2013). These structural realities pose fundamental challenges to the mainstream monetary policy consensus. The assumption that developing economies can replicate the institutions and strategies of high-income countries ignores differences in financial depth, economic diversification, and political economy. In settings where monetary transmission is weak, capital markets are underdeveloped, and the economy is highly exposed to external shocks, inflation targeting and interest rate rules may be ineffective or even counterproductive. Dollarized and non-sovereign economies such as Puerto Rico represent an extreme case of these difficulties, making visible the limits of orthodox monetary policy when key instruments of monetary sovereignty are structurally absent (Alemar & Rodríguez, 2025).

In summary, while mainstream frameworks such as those proposed by Friedman (1968) and Taylor (1993) have shaped global monetary policy norms, their applicability in developing economies is limited. Dollarization, in particular, highlights the constraints that arise when monetary sovereignty is absent. As Calvo and Reinhart (2002) and Mishra and Montiel (2013) demonstrate, the institutional and structural characteristics of developing countries require a more nuanced approach to monetary management. The following section explores how heterodox traditions have responded to these limitations, proposing alternative frameworks for understanding and conducting monetary policy in the Global South.

3. Heterodox Perspectives on Monetary Policy in Developing Economies

In contrast to the mainstream consensus around inflation targeting, central bank independence, and monetary neutrality, heterodox schools of economic thought offer fundamentally different visions of what monetary policy should be and how it functions in developing economies. Drawing on traditions such as Post-Keynesianism, Structuralism, and dependency theory, heterodox economists emphasize the political, institutional, and distributional dimensions of monetary policy. Rather than treating central banks as technocratic institutions devoted solely to price stability, these approaches position them as tools of development and agents of structural transformation (Lavoie, 2014; Epstein, 2006).

Post-Keynesian economics begins with the premise that money is endogenously created within the financial system. Banks issue loans based on the perceived creditworthiness of borrowers and their expected profitability, not according to prior reserves deposited at the central bank. In this framework, the central bank does not control the money supply directly but instead sets the price of liquidity through interest rates and regulatory frameworks. As Lavoie (2014) argues, central banks play a coordinating role within the financial system, but their capacity to manage inflation depends on the institutional context in which they operate. In developing economies, this context is often marked by incomplete markets, informal labor, and credit rationing, which make inflation targeting less effective and sometimes harmful. Post-Keynesians are particularly critical of the idea that inflation is the primary macroeconomic concern. In economies with large output gaps, underemployment, and infrastructure deficits, the focus on inflation can divert attention from more pressing developmental challenges. Furthermore, they argue that inflation in developing countries is frequently driven not by excess demand but by cost-push factors: exchange rate pass-through, commodity price volatility, or administrative pricing decisions. In such cases, raising interest rates to combat inflation can deepen recessions, raise unemployment, and stifle investment (Epstein, 2006). From this perspective, monetary policy must be integrated into a broader set of development tools, including fiscal expansion, public investment, and credit guidance.

Structuralist economists, influenced by the Latin American structuralist tradition of the mid-20th century, similarly reject the idea that monetary policy can be reduced to interest rate manipulation. For them, inflation and macroeconomic instability in developing countries are the result of deeper structural imbalances: a narrow export base, technological dependence, persistent trade deficits, and an underdeveloped financial sector. As such, stabilization cannot come from targeting monetary aggregates or inflation expectations but from addressing the structural causes of vulnerability (Dos Santos, 1970). Monetary policy, from a structuralist standpoint, is a tool that must be aligned with national development plans. Rather than isolating the central bank from political pressures, structuralists argue for a proactive coordination between monetary and fiscal authorities to finance long-term investments in infrastructure, education, and industrial capacity. Inflation may rise temporarily as a consequence of these efforts, but structuralists maintain that such trade-offs are acceptable if they lead to more resilient, inclusive growth.

Dependency theory offers an even more radical critique by situating monetary constraints within the broader framework of global capitalism. The theory, as articulated by economists such as Dos Santos (1970), argues that peripheral economies are structurally subordinated to the interests of the core, particularly through mechanisms of financial dependency. Developing countries, according to this view, are integrated into the global economy in ways that perpetuate inequality, technological backwardness, and political instability. Their monetary and fiscal policies are often shaped by the needs of creditors, multinational corporations, and international financial institutions rather than by domestic priorities. In this framework, the loss of monetary sovereignty, whether through dollarization, IMF conditionality, or external debt obligations, is not simply a technical issue but a form of neocolonial domination. Policies that prioritize inflation control, capital account liberalization, and debt repayment serve the interests of global finance but often undermine national development (Catalá Oliveras, 2016). Dependency theorists advocate for greater policy autonomy, including the use of capital controls, sovereign monetary policy, and a reorientation of central banks toward domestic goals. They also call for regional integration strategies, such as common monetary areas or development banks, to reduce reliance on external finance and enhance bargaining power in the global economy.

One of the most visible recent developments in heterodox monetary thinking is Modern Monetary Theory (MMT), popularized by economists such as Kelton (2020). MMT holds that states with monetary sovereignty, those that issue their own currency and borrow in it, are not constrained by revenue when it comes to spending. Such governments can finance any expenditure so long as there are real resources available in the economy; the constraint is not the fiscal deficit but the inflation threshold. From this perspective, fiscal policy is the primary lever for managing aggregate demand, and monetary policy should play a supportive role in maintaining low interest rates and facilitating full employment. Sharpe (2014) applies this logic to members of the Eurozone, arguing the inability to issue their own currency and set independent monetary policy severely constraints their capacity to pursue full employment and robust recovery, highlighting the importance of distinguishing between “issuers” and “users.”

While MMT is not directly applicable to economies that lack monetary sovereignty, its insights have nonetheless sparked important debates about the artificial constraints placed on government spending in developing countries. For example, in many low-income nations, fears of budget deficits and debt accumulation lead to austerity policies that weaken growth and social cohesion. Even in partially dollarized economies or those subject to IMF oversight, heterodox economists argue that targeted fiscal expansion can be financed through development banks, cooperative credit systems, or currency swap arrangements with friendly countries (Kelton, 2020). The goal is to reclaim policy space and prioritize developmental outcomes over the preferences of international creditors, however keeping in mind that balance-of-payments constraint and currency hierarchy can sharply limit fiscal space (Vernango & Pérez). An important corollary of these arguments is the need for local credit creation mechanisms. In the absence of full monetary sovereignty, developing economies can still cultivate financial autonomy by building institutions that allocate credit toward productive uses. Public banks, credit unions, and state-led development funds have played significant roles in the histories of countries like South Korea, Brazil, and India. These institutions can help finance industrial upgrading, agricultural modernization, and urban infrastructure even in contexts where central banks lack conventional tools (Epstein, 2006). In this sense, they function as partial substitutes for missing monetary instruments, expanding domestic policy space without necessarily altering the formal monetary regime.

Heterodox approaches also emphasize the importance of democratizing monetary policy. Rather than placing central banks in the hands of unelected technocrats, many heterodox scholars advocate for participatory governance structures that include labor unions, small business representatives, and

community organizations. This reflects a broader commitment to economic democracy and the idea that monetary policy should be accountable to the public it serves. In practice, this could involve setting employment targets alongside inflation targets, holding public consultations on monetary strategy, or integrating social indicators into central bank mandates.

Finally, heterodox schools tend to be more open to institutional innovation. In response to the perceived failures of orthodox policy, some countries have experimented with dual interest rate policies, directed credit schemes, or parallel currencies. While these tools carry risks, proponents argue that they can help overcome market failures and expand economic activity in marginalized areas. The key is to treat monetary policy not as a neutral instrument but as a set of choices that reflect social priorities and political struggles. For non-sovereign and dollarized economies, this often means focusing less on conventional interest rate policies and more on the architecture of the local financial institutions, fiscal arrangements, and development banks that can be deployed within the existing monetary constraints. To summarize, heterodox perspectives on monetary policy reject the narrow focus on inflation targeting and instead situate monetary institutions within a broader developmental and political context. Whether through the post-Keynesian focus on endogenous money, the Structuralist emphasis on production and trade structures, or the Dependency critique of global financial hierarchies, these approaches offer a more flexible and historically grounded framework for understanding the challenges faced by developing economies. They also open the door to alternative strategies that prioritize employment, social welfare, and long-term transformation over short-term stabilization. The following section will apply these insights to evaluate how territories with limited or no monetary sovereignty can still pursue policies that advance inclusive and sustainable development, using Puerto Rico as a case study of a small, dollarized economy whose real outcomes are closely tied to the monetary decisions of a foreign central bank (Alemar & Rodríguez, 2025).

4. Concluding Remarks: Puerto Rico as a Case Study in Monetary Dependence

The preceding sections have explored the theoretical foundations and practical limitations of monetary policy in developing economies from both mainstream and heterodox perspectives. In this final section, these insights are applied to the specific case of Puerto Rico, an economy that occupies a unique and highly constrained position within the global financial system. As a non-sovereign, dollarized territory of the United States, Puerto Rico lacks control over the basic instruments of monetary policy, including interest rate setting, currency issuance, and the regulation of liquidity. Its experience underscores the extreme consequences of monetary dependence and raises important questions about the possibilities for economic development in such conditions (Krueger, 2015; Catalá Oliveras, 2016).

Puerto Rico's monetary situation is unlike that of any U.S. state or sovereign developing country. It is fully integrated into the U.S. monetary system but lacks voting representation in the Federal Open Market Committee (FOMC) and has no ability to tailor monetary policy to local conditions. During periods of economic downturn, such as the long recession from 2006 to 2016, the island was unable to respond with monetary stimulus. Interest rates were set according to U.S. national indicators, not Puerto Rican realities, and liquidity operations were channeled through mechanisms largely outside the island's control. This lack of monetary autonomy exacerbated the fiscal crisis, deepened unemployment, and accelerated emigration (Krueger, 2015). Furthermore, as Alemar and Rodríguez (2025) show using a restricted VAR model, increases in U.S. interest rates explain a considerable amount of the variation in unemployment in Puerto Rico, while having little effect on local inflation, highlighting the asymmetric and costly transmission of U.S. monetary policy to the island's real economy.

In orthodox economic models, such rigid frameworks might be justified by the benefits of nominal stability. Dollarization, after all, eliminates currency risk, reduces transaction costs, and can help anchor inflation expectations (Calvo & Reinhart, 2002). But in Puerto Rico's case, these advantages have not translated into macroeconomic stability or growth. Instead, the island remains mired in a low-growth equilibrium, unable to pursue the kind of counter-cyclical policies typically available to sovereign states. The inability to devalue its currency or engage in expansionary monetary operations means that Puerto Rico must rely heavily on fiscal tools, tools that are themselves constrained by balanced budget requirements, legal oversight by the PROMESA fiscal board, and limited access to credit markets (Catalá Oliveras, 2016).

Moreover, the institutional configuration of Puerto Rico's economy mirrors many of the weaknesses identified by heterodox economists in other developing contexts. The financial sector is narrow, capital markets are underdeveloped, and credit is rationed, particularly in low-income and rural communities (Krueger, 2015). Public investment has declined under austerity, and infrastructure needs remain pressing. In this context, the absence of a local central bank or development finance institution is particularly acute. While credit unions and cooperatives play an important role in some sectors, their reach is limited, and they lack the scale to offset the withdrawal of public financial support (Epstein, 2006).

Puerto Rico's condition also resonates with the critiques advanced by dependency theorists. The island's political status and economic institutions are structured in ways that prioritize debt repayment and fiscal discipline over endogenous development. The PROMESA oversight board, established by the U.S. Congress in 2016, has broad powers to enforce fiscal targets, restructure debt, and oversee public budgets. While this may reassure creditors, it reduces local policy autonomy and reinforces a dynamic of external control (Dos Santos, 1970; Catalá Oliveras, 2016).

Nevertheless, some limited policy space remains. Local government, civil society, and cooperative institutions have all sought to develop alternative strategies within the constraints of the current framework. There have been efforts to expand community credit systems, promote worker cooperatives, and strengthen local agriculture and manufacturing. These initiatives align with heterodox calls for localized development, financial democratization, and credit creation outside traditional monetary channels (Lavoie, 2014; Epstein, 2006). They also reflect a growing recognition that development cannot be imported through external investment or federal transfers alone; it must be built from within, using the tools and institutions available.

Policy recommendations for Puerto Rico, and by extension for other non-sovereign or dollarized economies, must therefore focus on strengthening what autonomy remains. One key area is the expansion of local financial institutions capable of channeling credit toward socially productive investments. This includes not only credit unions and cooperatives, but also potential public development banks or municipal bond programs designed to finance infrastructure, housing, and small business growth. By redirecting capital toward domestic priorities, these institutions can help compensate for the lack of conventional monetary instruments (Epstein, 2006; Vernengo & Pérez, 2020).

Another recommendation involves rethinking fiscal policy under conditions of constraint. While balanced budgets are often imposed as a sign of fiscal responsibility, there is growing evidence that such rules can be procyclical and counterproductive in depressed economies. Within the PROMESA framework, there may be opportunities to reframe spending priorities toward investment and social stabilization rather than austerity. Negotiating these spaces will require both technical expertise and political mobilization, as well as new alliances between local actors and sympathetic policymakers in Washington.

Additionally, Puerto Rico might benefit from deeper regional cooperation in areas such as energy, transportation, and financial regulation. While full monetary integration with Latin America or the Caribbean is unlikely given its political status, technical partnerships or knowledge-sharing initiatives could provide valuable resources and reduce dependence on federal institutions. These forms of cooperation might also help lay the groundwork for longer-term structural reforms, including the potential reimagining of Puerto Rico's political status itself.

Future research should explore these themes in greater depth. There is a pressing need for empirical studies on how U.S. monetary policy affects economic cycles in Puerto Rico, particularly through credit markets, consumption, and investment. The VAR approach employed by Alemar and Rodríguez (2025) provides a useful starting point, but further work could extend their framework to include distributional outcomes, sectoral dynamics, or non-linear effects. There is also scope for comparative research on other dollarized economies, such as Ecuador or El Salvador, to better understand the institutional adaptations required under monetary constraint. Finally, more work is needed on the legal and political structures that condition economic governance in non-sovereign territories, with particular attention to how fiscal oversight mechanisms intersect with development planning.

In sum, Puerto Rico represents an extreme but illuminating case of monetary dependence. Its experience highlights the inadequacy of orthodox policy frameworks in contexts where monetary sovereignty is absent. It also illustrates the value of heterodox insights into the relationship between money, power, and development. For Puerto Rico, and for similar economies, the challenge is not simply to manage within existing constraints, but to reimagine what monetary and economic policy could look like in the absence of full sovereignty, and how development can proceed even under such structural limitations.

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